

CLASSIFICATION TECHNOLOGY IN HIGHER EDUCATION

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Abstract: *Pedagogical games are characterized by the style of play as follows: by subject; plot; business, imitation, dramatized games. All pedagogical games used in the system of higher, secondary special and vocational education are, in essence, business games. Because they are usually developed within a specific learning discipline: roles and plots are present, different situations are imitated. That is, business games used in the system of higher and secondary special vocational education include all components of pedagogical games.*

Keywords— Pedagogical play, general education, Individual teaching, learning process, standard, professional behavior, social action.

1. INTRODUCTION

In general education, academic lyceums and vocational colleges, there are both positive and negative aspects of stratification of students according to their level of intellectual development. For high school, however, there is no doubt about this teaching system. At present, the level of knowledge acquisition of university entrants ranges from 100% to 25%. In this context, the stratification of training in order to train highly qualified personnel in accordance with the requirements of state educational standards is a requirement of the times.

Ensuring that the student realizes the existing personal potential is a requirement of accelerated scientific and technological development of the modern educational process. This can be achieved through individual and individualized training.

2. MAIN PART

Individual teaching is a form of organization of the learning process, in which the educator deals with students individually, the student receives continuous independent learning using teaching aids (books, computers, etc.).

Advantages of individual teaching: is the possibility of adaptation of the pedagogical process to the abilities of the learner. At the same time, as a result of constant monitoring of the level of knowledge of the student and the necessary adjustments, an optimal pedagogical process is created.

Individual approach - this is a pedagogical principle, in the pedagogical process, the teacher's interaction with students is built taking into account their individual characteristics and creates a psychological and pedagogical environment for the development of the whole group and each individual student.

Individualized learning is based on an individual approach to the organization of such a learning process, the choice of ways, methods, pace of teaching and is provided through various educational-methodical psychological-pedagogical and organizational management measures.

Individual teaching technology - an individual approach to the organization of the learning process and the individual form of teaching is a priority. In all person-centered teaching technologies, an individual approach is used to some extent, but in individualized teaching, individualization is the main means of achieving learning goals. The basis of individualized teaching is the establishment of individual-pedagogical characteristics of the student. Based on the results obtained, the teaching method is selected. The teaching process is carried out according to the adopted technologies, rules and principles.

Material and methods: Student activity in the educational process has been and will remain one of the main principles of didactics. Student activism is the result of purposeful managerial pedagogical influences and the organization of the pedagogical environment. One of the teaching technologies that ensures the activity of students is a pedagogical business game. Interest in play activities is provided through elements of competition that meet the needs of students, such as self-expression and realization.

A great feature of the game is that it is both development and learning at the same time.

Pedagogical play is determined by the clearly defined goal of teaching and the corresponding pedagogical outcome. These results will be grounded and will have training activities.

Pedagogical games in the system of higher, secondary special and vocational education are aimed at mastering and strengthening new educational material, solving a set of problems that develop the creative abilities of students, the formation of general scientific skills. allows students to understand and learn learning material from a variety of situations. In the learning process, entrepreneurs use different forms of games: imitation, operative, role-playing games, working theater, psycho and socio-dramas.

The business game combines the form of restoration of the subject and social content of the future professional activity of the specialist, modeling the system of such relations, which determines the integrity of the activity.

Using specific tools (language, speech, graphs, tables, documents), a professional situation similar to the real situation is created in the business game according to the main important features. However, in a business game, only related general situations are restored in a short period of time.

The business game creates a subjective aspect of future professional activity (conditional practice), a social aspect in which learners interact with representatives of a different role situation. Thus, in the business game, team learning is carried out in a holistic form in the model of a holistic form of activity - production, conditions of professional activity.

In a business game, the learner performs a similar professional activity that combines educational and professional elements. The acquisition of knowledge and skills takes place not in the abstract, but in the context (meaning) of professional work. In contextual learning, knowledge is not in vain for the future, but provides the learner with movement in the real game process. At the same time, the student will gain professional knowledge as well as the ability to communicate and manage people with special traits, team decision-making skills, leadership and subordination skills. That is, the business game cultivates personal qualities, accelerates the process of socialization. But because this “serious” professional activity is realized in the form of a game, the student is mentally and emotionally liberated, showing creative initiative.

The dynamics of production serve as a business game, a tool for updating, applying and consolidating knowledge, and a tool for practical thinking, modeling and simulating the actions and attitudes of professionals. This is done through the interaction of the participants in a given specific situation of the game or in a production situation. The business game is implemented as a joint activity to set and solve game learning problems in a simulated model. The rules and norms of joint activity, the language of analogy and communication are accepted in advance or developed during the game. The business game is held in a rhythmic dialogue, it is a double activity, because it achieves two goals: playful and pedagogical. Although pedagogical activity is a priority, it should not disrupt the game.

During the game the following will be mastered:

- standards of professional behavior;
- norms of social action
- relations in the production team.

In doing so, each participant of the game is in an active state, interacts with his partners, compares his views with those of his partners, and as a result learns himself through his relationship with the team.

Simulation games - imitate the activities of the department, sex, enterprise organization. The simulation game scenario, in addition to the plot of the event, includes details about the structure and significance of the imitation process and objects.

Practical games are relevant work processes that model the conditions under which they are performed. They help to learn

a specific method: - to solve problems, to master a certain method.

Role-playing games are the mental states and behaviors of a particular person in the performance of tasks and responsibilities, the roles are distributed with mandatory content.

Business theater is the development of a situation and the behavior of a person in that situation. A scenario is drawn up detailing the situation, the tasks and responsibilities of the participants, and their goals. Here, it is important to get into the real image of a particular person, to understand his behavior, to assess the situation and to choose the right behavior.

3. REFERENCES

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